

**ПРОЕКТНАЯ РАБОТА ПО ДИСЦИПЛИНЕ «СТРАНОВЕДЕНИЕ
ИЗУЧАЕМОГО ЯЗЫКА»**

**PROJECT WORK IN A CLASS ON THE DISCIPLINE “REGIONAL STUD-
IES OF THE STUDIED LANGUAGE”**

ДЖУМАНОВА ЛЯЙЛЯ СЕЙТКАЗИЕВНА,

старший преподаватель,

Карагандинский университет имени академика Е.А. Букетова.

ТУРБАЕВА САЯ МУХАМЕДЖАНОВНА,

преподаватель,

Карагандинский университет имени академика Е.А. Букетова.

DZHUMANOVA LYAILYA SEITKASIEVNA,

Senior Lecturer,

Karaganda University named after Academician E.A. Buketov.

TURBAEVA SAYA MUKHAMEDZHANOVNA,

Lecturer,

Karaganda University named after Academician E.A. Buketov.

В статье рассматриваются перспективы применения проектной работы на уроках по дисциплине «Регионоведение изучаемого языка». Применение проектного подхода предполагает, что учащиеся ориентированы на сопоставление явлений, фактов из истории и жизни людей из разных стран. Приведены некоторые примеры заданий, позволяющих учащимся проявить самостоятельность в выборе темы, источников информации, способа ее подачи. Показано, что проектный метод позволяет учащимся реализовать свою изобретательность, используя критическое мышление и приобретенные знания. Подчеркивается, что использование проектного подхода требует учета индивидуальной работы преподавателя с учащимися.

The article discusses the prospects for the application of project work in the lessons of the discipline "Regional studies of the studied language". The application of the project approach assumes that students are focused on comparing phenomena, facts from history and the lives of people from different countries. Some examples of tasks are given that allow students to show independence in choosing a topic, sources of information, and the way it is presented. It is shown that the project method allows students to realize their ingenuity using critical thinking and acquired knowledge. It is emphasized that the use of the project approach requires taking into account the individual work of the teacher with the students.

Ключевые слова: *проектный метод, региональная география, языковой материал, культура страны, источники информации.*

Key words: *project method, regional geography, language material, culture of the country, sources of information.*

In the modern world, proficiency in at least one foreign language is considered the norm, even a requirement of the time. Knowledge of a foreign language, nowadays English, gives such advantages as: finding more information on the Internet in this language, communicating with

native speakers without a translator (not all translators can convey the meaning and the whole essence of what is said), understanding computer programs, reading books and publishing world-famous classics in the original, watching fiction and documentaries films in the language, listening to the origin and pronunciation of some words, phrases and linguistic phenomena, as well as knowing their application in life situations.

Project work plays an important role in learning foreign languages. When performing project work, students choose a topic themselves, conduct research, make a plan for further work, and eventually provide all the work done in the form of a presentation. Project work helps students not only to supplement their knowledge with additional information, but also helps them to think independently and think creatively.

The use of project work in the classroom has become an interesting and effective method for learning foreign languages, allowing you to create and consolidate regional knowledge in the discipline "Regional studies of the studied language", make an independent and reasoned decision, draw informed conclusions, learn how to work in a team, forming a communicative competence.

Teachers should use various sources for teaching the local lore, one of the most important of them is the newspaper. At the university, however, you don't just have to work with the complicated, demanding specialist articles. In every newspaper you will find simple, short texts, which are often supplemented by graphics. Here are two examples of newspaper texts that are well suited for university work.

An interesting document of local lore, which can be found in every newspaper, is the television program. „Television shapes the everyday life of most people, and even the program can tell us a lot about this everyday life“ [1, p.19; 8; 9]. Television plays an important role for students these days, and this should be used.

You can work with the program in different ways. The teacher is very good at persuading students to communicate by talking about the programs. Various things can be discussed:

- Which German programs do you know?
- Do you or someone from your family have satellite TV?
- Do you know some movies?
- Which program structure do you prefer, e.g. Pro7 or Nova?

Through this comparison and this contrastiveness, the students become aware of the differences. The teacher can prepare various questions in advance, which then need to be answered. In „Landeskunde mit der Zeitung“, for example, some questions are formulated that can be asked to the students. I introduce a few examples:

- How many programs are there?
- When does the show start and end?
- What student programs are there?
- Which series are there and where do they come from?
- On which program can you watch the most student programs?

Group work is excellent for working with the television program. Students can take out various information from the program in groups.

Students can be given a task in which they should write down messages from all programs. The groups can then discuss:

- Who found the most;
- Whether all of them are really messages;
- Which program has the most news;
- Whether, perhaps, there is a special program that focuses only on news, etc.

This gives the lesson a communicative character.

Another task is to write down all the broadcasts that are worth watching for the students. To do this, you will need to record the exact program and time, and then tell us why you chose this particular program. This will force the students to communicate again. Another part of each newspaper, which is not so difficult for the students, is the weather report. You can work very well with the weather report, because the graphic design of a map is combined with a short text. On the one hand, students can learn new words related to the weather, on the other hand, they learn about the geography of the German-speaking countries and also about the climate there, which can then be compared with the climate in Kazakhstan.

Some suggestions for working with a weather map can be found in the book „Landeskunde mit der Zeitung“. Here are some examples:

- Name the countries on the weather map and their capitals;
- Specify which cities the student has registered;
- Describe the weather in individual regions;
- Plan the tour depending on what the weather is like there.

The teacher can also get several weather maps and let the student guess for which day (exact day, month or only season) the weather report would be suitable. Each group can get their own weather map and then justify their opinion before the class. Some role-playing games were also to be found in the selected textbooks, which more or less focused on regional studies. In the role-playing game proposed by me, the regional background is undisputed. The role-playing game is called "City Guide". This role-playing game requires for student preparation. A student (or several) should get information about a city from Germany, Austria, Liechtenstein or Switzerland by the next hour. He can also get various pictures and photos of sights from the chosen city, which can then be glued or hung in the group. In the lesson, he then introduces the city and the other students have the role of tourists or visitors. The student then organizes the fictitious implementation, the others can contact him with various questions. This leads to the deepening of knowledge about different cities and the development of communicative competence [2, p. 52].

This role-playing game can be carried out throughout the academic year. For example, you can organize two project work sessions per month. The city guides can then get a good grade for the same research.

Since the textbooks do not have enough suggestions for project lessons, I would like to present here three games for project work. As an option, you can consider the project “A trip to Vienna.” But the city can be chosen at will. The preparation of this project is quite difficult, so it is recommended for undergraduates.

The preparation of this project is quite demanding, so it is recommended for older students. In this project, the students are to plan and prepare a trip to Vienna themselves. The teacher has the function of a consultant. Ideally, the planned trip could actually be realized. The intensive study of the Austrian capital gives students the opportunity to get to know and understand the life, history and present of the city. Since the students themselves determine what they would like to see and visit in Vienna, their motivation and interest increases. This project work can be organized as a group work (two groups), where each group has different tasks [3, p. 21].

You can use the Internet, various maps and brochures. The teacher can get some materials. A group may be responsible for the trip. You should find a cheap variant. You should inquire about the schedule, duration of the trip, prices, discounts and booking options. The other group should determine what are the possible sights and monuments to see in Vienna. You also need to ask about the opening hours and about entrance fees. Students have to decide what they want to see and visit – all students are involved in this. You should then prepare an interesting program and a schedule together. If this excursion is then really realized, the learners can get an idea of whether their preparation was sufficient and what could still be improved [4, p. 27].

Let's consider another project "Cities of Switzerland". (Another country can be defined here again.) For this project the children would need about German lessons.

Even before you start your own project work, some things need to be clarified. It should also be explained how the project should look like in the end, or rather some examples should be shown. It should have the form of a poster. All details have to be clarified – the intention of the project, the duration, etc. The students should visit all sorts of things about Switzerland and bring them with them to the next lesson – e.g. newspapers, magazines, brochures, postcards, books, photos... At this time, a conversation should be held about what the others already know about Switzerland. The teacher should bring the card from Switzerland. He may ask some of the following questions:

Where is Switzerland located anyway? Which countries does it border with? How do you speak in Switzerland? Have you visited her yet? (or how did you go there, which cities did you visit and what did you see there?) How big is Switzerland? How many people live here? What is the name of the capital? How many cantons are there in Switzerland? Which rivers flow through Switzerland? What is the name of the highest mountain and how high is it? What does the flag look like? What is the name of the currency in Switzerland? Which Swiss cities do you know? Do you know some Swiss personalities (actors, athletes, politicians, musicians...)?

Do you have any acquaintances or relatives in Switzerland?

Then the most important information must be summarized on a large sheet. Someone can write down the headline, one can draw the Swiss flag, one paints a small map of Switzerland with individual cantons, some summarize the main information in the short (size, number of inhabitants, capital ...), someone writes down the countries that border Switzerland, etc. It should already be clear which city which group has chosen [5, p.13].

Students can use the Internet to try to find out even more information about their cities. The groups then have to summarize the most important information about their city and convert it into simple sentences. It is then glued to the large sheet.

Students can use the Internet to try to find out even more information about their cities. Then the groups must summarize the most important information about their city and convert it into simple sentences. Then it is pasted on a large sheet.

The last hour of work on the project will be devoted to the presentation. The groups introduce each other to their cities. The student observers can then evaluate each work. Then a poster with all the information about Switzerland and individual cities should be hung somewhere on the wall or pasted on a blackboard in the classroom. When the posters of both groups are hung in the most visible place, students may feel that they have done something important. At the end of the lesson, the groups should discuss how successful the project was, what could be done better next time, what the students found difficult, whether they liked it, etc.

Such forms are great for studying regional studies, with the help of which the student not only learns facts and information, but also experiences something that he will remember for a long time. The culture of German-speaking countries should be conveyed to the student not only with the help of a teacher, textbook or other media, but also in German classes he can get to know it himself. According to my suggestion, the student can work not only with his head and hands, but also with his imagination [6, p.7].

As part of these project activities, students can also get acquainted with typical dishes of German-speaking countries. The ideal way to get acquainted with the cuisine of these countries is to cook a dish according to the recipe of some German-speaking country, bring it to class and treat students to it. This is an ideal way to brighten up the lesson not only with theory, but also with the practical part. Of course, there are many recipes that can be found not only in a cookbook, but also in magazines or on the Internet.

Cooking stews is very interesting (and delicious) for students. In most cases, students cannot accurately determine the meaning of this word, and the explanation in the dictionary does not help

much either. If students want to cook something, they need at least two German classes in a row, which can be a problem. But the teacher will certainly find the right solution to this problem. It is also necessary that the group has a working kitchen. Even before starting cooking, it is necessary to discuss all the details in an hour and carefully read the recipe [7, p.48].

When performing this work, it is important that students not only learn a lot of new words, but that they get to know a new taste through tasting, and that learning is combined with a new experience.

Regional studies is an extensive, but at the same time an interesting topic of foreign language teaching for both teachers and students. You can imagine the most diverse areas of life under her. It gives us a vivid picture of the strange reality. It is difficult to learn the German language without a connection with regional studies.

As part of the article, we tried to show which sources, materials and media a teacher can use in regional studies lessons. This is how they outlined what duties the teacher has and what problems are associated with regional studies.

We hope that the suggestions and examples presented on the introduction of regional studies in German lessons, presented in the last part, will help other teachers to make their lessons more interesting and effective. The proposed examples represent only a small part of all the possibilities. In practice, it always depends on the specific teacher, on his skills and his ability to improvise, how he can attract and captivate students to learn the local lore.

СПИСОК ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

1. Jenkins E.M. Landeskundliches Lernen in: Fremdsprache Deutsch. 1/1998. P. 18-23.
2. Steinig W., Huneke H.W., Landeskunde in DaF.-Berlin, 1998. P. 51-52.
3. Łakowski R., Marcinkowski R. Encyclopedia Popularna PWN. Warszawa, 2007. P. 21-22
4. Erdmenger M. Didaktik der Landeskunde, Munich. 2009. P. 8-30.
5. Badstübner-Kizik C., Radziszewska K. Austrian, German and Polish identities in: Foreign Language German. 1998. №3.
6. Hackl W., Langner M. Landeskundliches Lernen in: Fremdsprache Deutsch, 3/1998.
7. Heyd G. Teaching German. Frankfurt a. M., 2009. P. 47-52.
8. Zum Erwerb der interkulturellen Kompetenz in Zeiten der Digitalisierung // Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi. 2021. DOI:10.52642/susbed.910561
9. Hammadi A. Didaktik der Landeskunde im Fremdsprachenunterricht: Wie kann Landeskunde die kommunikative Fähigkeit erweitern und verbessern? GRIN Verlag. 2020. 40 p.

© Джуманова Л.С., Турбаева С.М., 2024.